

SMART CITY: IS IT POSSIBLE TO LIFE WITHOUT TRAFFIC?

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Annotation: *Often a person is forced to spend his time in traffic jams. If we compare the city and a living organism, then the roads will be the circulatory system. The movement of people and traffic flows is called traffic, it is controlled by hundreds of traffic lights that act as valves in our heart. Some valves are closed and allow flow, then vice versa. Plugs are a blood clot, and as you know, the appearance of blood clots in the human body can lead to death. Unfortunately, today our city regularly suffers from the formation of such blood clots.*

Key words: *City, roads, traffic jams, transport, car, accident (traffic accident), sharp turn, rise, speed bumps.*

Modern cities are like living organisms with a large number of vital organs: the heart of the city is its inhabitants, the brain is the local authorities, and the nervous system is the communication system. Each organ must properly interact with each other for the health of the whole organism [1].

The theme of the first issue is smart cities. Today, 6.7% of the world's population lives in cities, and by 2050, 68% of all people on the planet will live in them. Megacities are not only gigantic islands of opportunity, but also the main producers of waste, exhaust gases, consumers of energy and time wasters for traffic jams and travel. It seems that a big city is not created for a person, and a person is not created for a big city.

The city is not just an architecturally organized whole, immortalized in space. The city is, first of all, people who walk, drive and wander along the streets and roads. It is not for nothing that they say that city life is an eternal vanity. People are constantly in a hurry somewhere, busy with something, but for some reason they do not have time to do anything. I want to start my article with the concept of time. Time is an irreversible current that flows in only one direction (from the past, through the present and into the future). But above all, time is the main resource in the urban environment.

Roads are a sign of space. Almost all roads in Central Asia were designed about 2000 years ago. As it is not surprising, but most modern roads repeat the pattern of those roads.

The average city dweller spends about 2 hours a day in public transport. This is 730 hours a year. Half of this time he spends on the way to work from home and vice versa. Often a person is forced to spend his time in traffic jams. If we compare the city and a living organism, then the roads will be the circulatory system. The movement of people and traffic flows is called traffic, it is controlled by hundreds of traffic lights that act as valves in our heart.

Some valves are closed and allow flow, then vice versa. Plugs are a blood clot, and as you know, the appearance of blood clots in the human body can lead to death. Unfortunately, today our city regularly suffers from the formation of such blood clots.

The state is starting to build new roads to relieve the load, but this has the opposite effect, causing additional traffic and road congestion increases. You need to actively use public transport, and not a private car. In Singapore, half of all trips in the city are made by public transport. They were able to achieve this by making not only all roads and parking in the center paid, but the car itself costs 6 times more than in other countries [2].

The most common causes of irregular traffic jams are not only weather conditions, but above all, the road users themselves. Most people on the road like to always rush, not noticing the situation around them. On the road, safety is paramount. In Sweden, they solved the problem of careless driving in a very non-standard way, by changing the left-hand traffic to the right-hand drive in 1967 [3].

Mortality in traffic accidents (traffic accident) in the year of transition decreased by 20%, as drivers found themselves in unfamiliar conditions and tried to drive carefully. This did not allow people to relax on the road.

The traffic jam is created as follows: if one person slows down, then the cars behind him will also slow down in turn until the speed of one of the driver drops to 0, thereby creating a “phantom intersection” [4].

Such plugs can stretch from 100 to 1000 meters. An experiment was conducted where drivers were told to drive at the same speed around the ring and keep the same interval between cars, but the drivers could not move smoothly and traffic jams began to form endlessly. It turns out that the person and the decisions made by him are to blame. But what if we remove the human factor altogether? For cars to move smoothly.

If one car slows down, it will give a signal to other cars and they, in turn, will gradually reduce speed, which will not lead to a complete stop. If all cars become autonomous, then there will be no need to control traffic and complete stops of the car will not be required [5].

Two intersecting streams will pass through each other without stopping, and all because the cars coordinate their movements and keep the right distance.

A similar principle can be observed in ants. Make of all the traffic in the city, one smart mechanism. But mechanisms have a tendency

to wear out and break. So here, no one is insured that because of one small mistake the whole system can collapse. Well, what to do while we do not have such technologies in mass production. Shared space comes to the rescue. The absence of signs and priorities makes each participant in the movement more attentive. This principle exists in the UK, Thailand, Italy. This will return, in a good way, to the 19th century, when cars moved very slowly and did not pose a threat to pedestrians.

There is one more road user, apart from the driver and the pedestrian, and this is the urban environment itself. In dangerous places where a pedestrian and a driver can collide, special conditions are made so that the driver does not have the opportunity to accelerate the car more than 30 km / h, it is this speed that is considered "safe" for a collision. This is achieved by physical obstacles: sharp turns, climbs, speed bumps.

In my opinion, the most ideal solution for sleeping areas is to use a hippodam net. The hippodamic grid is a method of planning ancient cities with streets intersecting at right angles, equal rectangular quarters and areas allocated for public buildings and markets, a multiple of the standard size of a quarter [6].

So, for example, in Barcelona (Spain), quarters were combined into super-quarters, in which trucks and buses are prohibited from entering, and only personal vehicles can enter inside, with a maximum permitted speed of 10 km / h.

So is it possible to create a "smart city" without traffic jams and accidents? These are questions about technology, but about people and their behavior. When we change selfishness for partnership, only then will it become safer and more comfortable on the roads.

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